

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№3

2025-YIL APREL. NAVBATDAN TASHQARI SON

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 441 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 1-aprelda ruxsat etildi.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

- Salimov Okil Umrzokovich**, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridakhon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 28-fevraldagi 333/5-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

ПРИНЦИПЫ ПЕРЕХОДА УЗБЕКИСТАНА К ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ, СУЩЕСТВУЮЩИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВНЫЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ	12
Набиев Дилмурод Хамидуллаевич	
YaShIL TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA RAQAMLASH TIRISH TA'SIRIDA MEHNAT BOZORINING TRANSFORMASIYASI	19
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xo'jaevich	
РОЛЬ ТВОРЧЕСКОГО ТРУДА В ПОВЫШЕНИИ ЕГО ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ	26
Гулямов Саидахор Саидахмедович, Икрамов Мурат Акрамович, Очилов Акрам Одилович	
BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHNI TA'MINLASH MAQSADIDA "YASHIL IQTISODIYOT"GA O'TISH ZARURATI	33
O.X. Hamidov, D.Sh. Yavmutov	
ESG-ИНСТРУМЕНТАРИЙ КАК ФАКТОР УСИЛЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ РЕГИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	38
Татьяна Юрьевна Анопченко, Сергей Вадимович Ревунов, Роман Вадимович Ревунов	
TRANSITION OF RUSSIAN REGIONS TO A CLOSED-LOOP ECONOMY	49
Nikonov Sergey Mikhailovich, Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Filipenko Alexander Alexandrovich	
"YASHIL" IQTISODIYOTNING MOHIYATI VA TUZILISHI	53
Navruz-Zoda Baxtiyor Negmatovich	
ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА КАК ДРАЙВЕР УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ РЫНКА ТРУДА И МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ РАБОЧИХ МЕСТ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	59
Зокирова Нодира Каландаровна	
KREATIV IQTISODIYOT VA UNING INDUSTRIYA TURLARINING NAZARIY MASALALARI	64
Mamayunus Pardaev, Obid Pardaev, Akram Ochilov	
EKOLOGIK OMILLARNI HISOBGA OLGAN HOLDA BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHDA ERISHISH	73
Saidov Muhammadali Hakimovich, Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Esanbekov Diyorbek Mirzabek o'g'li	
INNOVASION TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA MEVA-SABZAVOTCHILIK MAHSULOTLARI KOOPERASIYASINING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	81
Raxmatulla Ergashev	
KARTOSHKKA MOSLANUVCHAN NAVLARI TURLI EKISH MUDDATLARI VA MULCHALASHLARDA HOSILDORLIGI HAMDA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIK KO'RSATKICHLARI	86
Ostonaqulov Toshtemir Eshimovich, Toshpulatova Surayyo Tulqin qizi, Ismayilov Alisher Isroilovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT – INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISHNING KALITI	90
Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanakovich, Usmonov Murodjon Dusmurot o'g'li	
ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ «ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ» В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН	93
Сайёра Насимовна Хамраева	
SABZAVOT (SHIRIN) MAKKAJO'XORI AJRATILGAN MOSLANUVCHAN NAV-DURAGAYLARINI ASOSIY VA TAKRORIY EKINLAR SIFATIDA TURLI MUDDATLARDA YETISHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI	97
Ostonaqulov Toshtemir Eshimovich, Nurillaev Ilhom Xolbek o'g'li, Jabborov Botir Shukurovich	
ZAMONAVIY BOZOR MUNOSABATLARIDA SAVDONI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY VA USLUBIY JIHATLARI	101
Ivatov Irisbek	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	105
Yadgarov Akram Akbarovich, Abdiyeva Flora Botir qizi	
GREEN ECONOMY: GLOBAL PERSPECTIVE AND UZBEKISTAN'S PATH	110
Dilmurod Mirza-Akhmedovich Rasulev, Dildorakhon Ulugbek kizi Shomuradova	
OLIV TA'LIM XIZMATLARINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TARG'IB QILISH BO'YICHA XORIJ TAJRIBASI	113
Musayev Bekjon Shukurillayevich	

TURIZM INDUSTRIYASINI BARQAROR STRATEGIK RIVOJLANTIRISHDA QO'LLANILADIGAN USULLAR TAHLILI	116
Turdibekov Xasan Ibragimovich	
ЗЕЛЁНОЕ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЕ И ФАКТОРЫ ЕГО РАЗВИТИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	120
Орипов Ильхом Абдуллаевич	
Перспективы развития цифровой трансформации в Республике Узбекистан	128
Мусабеков Джорабек Хакимджанович, Воронин Сергей Александрович	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT – BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHNING MUHIM OMILI SIFATIDA.....	133
G.Erkayeva	
Barqaror ish o'rinlarini yaratishda yashil iqtisodiyotning o'rni	138
Qo'chqorov G'aybulla Fayzullayevich, Qo'ziyeva Shaxnoza Bozor qizi	
ПРОБЛЕМЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	141
Фазлитдин Бахадирович Аминов	
RESPUBLIKADA EKOLOGIK TOZA MAHSULOT YETISHTIRISH ASOSIDA ELEKTRON SAVDONI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	145
Q. J. Mirzayev, F. F. Ulug'murodov	
Qoraqalpog'istonda sanoatni restruktizatsiyalash va yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish: muammolar, istiqbollar va statistik tahlillar	150
Abipova Gulmira Salavatdinovna	
CHORVACHILIK XO'JALIKLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA AGLOMERATSIYANING AHAMIYATI.....	153
Xusainov Oybek Jabborovich	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA STRATEGIYASINING KOMPANIYA UCHUN AHAMIYATI.....	156
Ergashev Toxir Kurbanovich, Toxirova Nigora Zokirjon qizi	
CHORVACHILIK KLASSTERLARI VA AGLOMERATSION RIVOJLANISH: O'ZARO TA'SIR VA SYNERGIYALAR	161
Xusainov Oybek Jabborovich 161	
HUDUDLARNING INNOVATSIYON SALOHİYATINI VAHOLASH	165
J.A. Ismatullayev, A. Do'lanov	
СОСТОЯНИЕ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	171
Нафасов Тохиржон, Г. П. Эркаева	
Mamlakatimizda ishsizlikni kamaytirishga qaratilgan islohotlar.....	174
Djurayev Olimjon Narkulovich	
USE OF THE ADVANCED EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES OF FARMING AND HOUSEHOLDS....	178
Ochilova Nargiza Akramovna	
SHAHAR AGLOMERATSIYALARINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH OMILLARI.....	181
Xidayatova Nigora Shorakibovna	
IQTISODIY O'SISHDA MEHNAT MIGRATSIYASINING AHAMIYATI.....	184
Djurayev Olimjon Narkulovich, Saidakbarov Jamshid Ne'matullo o'g'li	
TURIZMNIDA RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TRANSPORT XIZMATLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	189
Qosimov Jahongir	
РЫНОК ГОСТИНИЧНЫХ УСЛУГ В ТУРИЗМЕ В УСЛОВИЯХ ДИВЕРСИФИКАЦИИ И ДЕМОКРАТИЗАЦИИ ГОСТИНИЧНОЙ ИНДУСТРИИ.....	192
Ташмаматов Садирдин Нажмиддинович	
O'zbekistonda turizm sohasida faoliyat yuritayotgan kadrlar malakasini oshirishda dual ta'limdan foydalanishni boshqarish.....	196
Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Xamidova Mo'tabarxon Abdumalik qizi	
МАКТАБГАЧА ТА'ЛИМ TASHKILOTLARIDA AUTSORSING XIZMATLARIDAN FOYDALANISH MEKANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	201
Nasiba Ergasheva	
KORXONALARDA XODIMLARNI BOSHQARISHNING ASOSIY TAMOYILLARI	207
Djurayev Olimjon Narkulovich, Nurullayeva Vazira O'ktamovna	
ЗЕЛЁНЫЕ ИНВЕСТИЦИИ: ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ И РИСКИ	211
Номазов Бахром Бобомурадович	

ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ПРИНЦИПОВ ESG В ФИНАНСОВУЮ СФЕРУ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	215
Алимова Азиза Шерзатовна	
THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES ON MANAGEMENT	219
Ergashev Tokhir Kurbanovich, Tohirova Nigora Zokirjon kizi	
ЎЗБЕКISTONNING “YASHIL IQTISODIYOT STRATEGIYASI”NI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING ZARURIYATI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	224
Ergasheva Nazira Muratovna, Soyibov Mirjon Bekjonovich	
ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ УСЛУГ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРЫ, ВЛИЯЮЩИХ НА ПОВЫШЕНИЕ УРОВНЯ И КАЧЕСТВА ЖИЗНИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ	227
Алимова Муниса Юлчиевна	
РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ОБУВНОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ КАК ФАКТОР ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЕЁ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ЗНАЧИМОСТИ.....	232
Расулов Нозимжон Набиджонович	
AGLOMERATSIYA VA IQTISODIY O‘SISH: SABAB–OQIBAT ALOQASI (QASHQADARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	236
Xidoyatova Nigora Shorakibovna	
KORXONALARNING SOLIQ IDORALARIDA HISOBGA OLINISHIDAN HOSIL BO‘LGAN ORTIQCHA TO‘LOVLARINI VOJXONA TO‘LOVLARIDA HISOBGA OLISH MEKANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	239
Boykabilov Bahodir Mustafaevich	
UZOQ MUDDATLI AKTIVLARGA INVESTITSIYALAR HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI	242
Egamberdiyeva Salima Rayimovna, Bozorov Yashnarbek Xayrulla o‘g‘li	
ORGANIK QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGIDA “IXTISOSLASHTIRILGAN AGROKOOPERATIV” TASHKIL ETISH ORQALI TA‘MINOT ZANJIRI BOSHQARUVINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	248
Amirqulov Shuxrat Olimovich	
MAMLAKATIMIZDA OLIY TA‘LIM MUASSASALARINING MOLIYAVIY RESURSLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHI UCHUN ZAMONAVIY HUQUQIY ASOSLARI.....	254
Xayriddinov Shuxrat Botirovich	
TURIZMNING MADANIY-TARIXIY RESURSLARI: ASOSIY TUSHUNCHALAR VA TAMOYILLAR	258
Ruzmanov Dilshod Usmanovich	
BARQAROR TURIZM DESTINATSIYALARINING SIG‘IMINI BAHOLASH METODIKASI.....	262
Ibroximov Nodirbek Xasanovich	
ВОЗОБНОВЛЯЕМЫЕ ИСТОЧНИКИ ЭНЕРГИИ КАК ОСНОВА ЗЕЛеноЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В УЗБЕКISTANE	266
Хусаинов Равшан Рахимович	
ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ МАРКЕТИНГ И ПОВЕДЕНИЕ ПОТРЕБИТЕЛЕЙ.....	272
Раимова Муборак Джураевна	
“YASHIL IQTISODIYOT”NING ASOSIY XUSUSIYATLARI	276
Djumayev Asqar Xaydarovich	
RAQAMLI MARKETINGNING ISTE‘MOLCHI XULQ-ATVORIGA TA’SIRI.....	281
Raimova Muborak Jurayevna, Dilmurodov O‘tkir	
HUUDUDNING IJTIMOIY-IQTISODIY SALOHİYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH OMILLARI	287
SH.A. Buriyev	
SAVDO XIZMATLARINING ASOSIY FAOLIYAT KO‘RSATKICHLARI TIZIMINI BAHOLASH.....	291
Muxamedova Aziza Ravshanovna	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA GLOBAL IQLIM O‘ZGARISHI: YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING IQLIM O‘ZGARISHINI YENGISHDAGI O‘RNI VA GLOBAL HAMKORLIK.....	295
Usmonov Murodjon Xolmurod o‘g‘li, Ulug‘bek Eshmaxmatov	
КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНЫЕ ОСНОВЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ МЕХАНИЗМА НАЛОГОВОГО АДМИНИСТРИРОВАНИЯ НА ПРИМЕРЕ УЗБЕКISTANA.....	299
Абдулов Дамир Рустамович	
ЎЗБЕКISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O‘TISH ISTIQBOLLARI	305
Yuldashev Shamsiddin Qiyamiddinovich, Boliyeva Baxora Farxodovna	

ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА: КОНЦЕПЦИИ, ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ.....	308
Туляганова Шахноза Самукджановна	
O‘TA ERTAGI TARVUZNING HIMOYALANGAN JOYLAR UCHUN MOSLANUVCHAN NAV VA DURAGAYLARINI AJRATISH, ULARNI TURLI O‘G‘IT ME‘YORLARIDA HOSILDORLIGI VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI.....	311
Ostonaqulov Toshtemir Eshimovich, Amirov Xamidulla Suyunovich, Umirova Durdona Muqum qizi	
ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ПЛОДООВОЩНОЙ ОТРАСЛИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	315
Уралов Элшод, Вельм М.В.	
DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY AS A MODEL OF PROGRESS IN HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN.....	320
Abdiev Alimardon	
ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СЕКТОРА ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ СЛУЖБЫ И РАЗВИТИЯ КАДРОВОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА.....	322
Мухаммадбобур Салимов	
KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATI RIVOJLANISHIGA TA‘SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR.....	326
Suyunov Jabbor Mahmudovich	
“SALOHIYAT” TUSHUNCHASINING MAZMUNI VA IQTISODIY-IJTIMOY MOHIYATI.....	331
Zoirov G‘olibjon Toshtemir o‘g‘li	
DAVLAT BOSHQARUVIDA SUN‘IY INTELLEKTDAN FOYDALANISHNING AHAMIYATI	334
Salimov Muhammadbobur Qodir o‘g‘li	
O‘QUV JARAYONLARINI TASHKIL ETISH VA BOSHQARISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH	337
Tilakov Sherzod	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVNING XALQARO TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA BOSHQARUV SIFATINI OSHIRISHDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING AHAMIYATI.....	340
Sattarov Umirzoq, Ro‘ziev Zafar Ikromovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA O‘ZBEKISTONDA SANOAT XOM ASHYOLARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH TENDENSIYALARI.....	343
Xazratov Sarvar Ibragimovich	
YURTIMIZDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA KADRLAR TAYYORLASHNING ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALARI	348
G‘aniyev Shaxzod Shuhrat o‘g‘li, O‘rinov Diyorbek Xolmo‘min o‘g‘li	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATI O‘QUV MARKAZLARI VA KURSLARINI BOSHQARISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH	353
Tilakov Sherzod Akbarovich	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA MAHSULOT ISHLAB CHIQRISH VA SOTISH SIFATI HAMDA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA XODIMLARNI BOSHQARISH YO‘NALISHLARI.....	357
Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Ziyodullayeva Marjona Alisher qizi	
OMMAVIY TADBIRLAR YORDAMIDA TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH: O‘ZBEKISTON VA XALQARO TAJRIBA.....	360
Ibragimov Sardorbek Xusanovich	
Анализ цифровой трансформации и её влияния на привлечение инвестиций в регионы Узбекистана.....	365
Рахмонова Дурдона Хасан кизи	
Korxonada moliyaviy salohiyatini baholashning statistik tahlili.....	370
M.O. Musurmonova	
DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF THE BANKING SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	377
Kadirov Lutfulla Khalimovich	
PROBLEMS OF EMPLOYMENT IN THE LABOR MARKET OF UZBEKISTAN AND STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS FOR THEIR SOLUTION	381
Sharopov Temirmalik Rustam o‘g‘li	

“YASHIL” IQTISODIYOT TAMOYILLARI ORQALI QASHQADARYO VILOYATI SANOAT KOMPLEKSINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	385
U.Shukurov	
Foreign experiences in attracting investments in service industries	390
Hazratkulov Shahboz Boboqul oqli	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTDA TA'LIMNING ROLI	394
Babayeva Lola Ibragimovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISHI UCHUN DAVLAT TOMONIDAN YARATILAYOTGAN IMKONIYATLAR.....	398
Xudoyorov Azizbek Avaz o'g'li	
OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA TA'LIM SIFATINI YAXSHILASHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI.....	404
Safarov Sh. S.	
IJTIMOIIY MENEJMENTDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA ULARNI O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA JORIY ETISH ISTIQBOLLARI	408
G'aniyev Shaxzod Shuhrat o'g'li, Davronova Farangiz	
«Государственный финансовый контроль: Казначейский контроль в бюджетном процессе и перспективы его развития».....	415
Файзуллаева Зилола Равшановна, Д.Х. Пулатов	
YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHNING ASOSIY JIHATLARI.....	421
Urozoza Shaxlo Hasan qizi, Hazratqulov Shahboz Boboqul o'g'li	
OLIY TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA ULARNI O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA JORIY ETISH ISTIQBOLLARI	427
Safarov Shoxrux Sattor o'g'li	
PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF HUMAN RESOURCES IN UZBEKISTAN	431
Alimardonova Gulfizoda Alimardon kizi	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA KAPITAL QO'YILMALAR HISOBINI TO'G'RI TASHKIL ETISHNING AHAMIYATI	434
Egamberdiyeva Salima Rayimovna	

FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN SERVICE INDUSTRIES

Hazratkulov Shahboz Boboqul ogli

Teacher of the Department of Economics

Karshi State University

Email:shahbozhazratqulov@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-5600-6251>

Abstract: This article explores the risks that arise in attracting investments in service sectors and their foreign experience in managing them, including ways to regulate investment activities in the United States, the United Kingdom, Germany, France, China, Japan.

Key words: investment, investment activities, stock market, production, legislation, credit organizations, investment activity, investment, risk management, financial diversification, insurance system, digital technologies.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlariga investitsiyalarni jalb qilishda yuzaga keladigan risklar va ularni boshqarish bo'yicha xorijiy tajribasi o'rganiladi, jumladan, AQSH, Buyuk Britaniya, Germaniya, Fransiya, Xitoy, Yaponiyada investitsiya faoliyatini tartibga solish yo'llari o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: investitsiya, investitsiya faoliyati, fond bozori, ishlab chiqarish, qonunchilik, kredit tashkilotlari, investitsion faollik, investitsiya, risklarni boshqarish, moliyaviy diversifikatsiya, sug'urta tizimi, raqamli texnologiyalar.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуется зарубежный опыт управления рисками при привлечении инвестиций в сервисные сети, в том числе способы регулирования инвестиционной деятельности в США, Великобритании, Германии, Франции, Китае, Японии.

Ключевые слова: инвестиции, инвестиционная деятельность, фондовый рынок, производство, законодательство, кредитные организации, Инвестиционная активность, инвестиции управление рисками, финансовая диверсификация, система страхования, цифровые технологии.

Currently, the sustainable growth of investment volumes and their effective use is one of the tactical and strategic tasks. Its successful solution involves a comprehensive consideration of the complex interdependence of many elements of the investment sphere inherent in the investment process. It is known from the experience of economically developed countries that the consistent implementation of the relationship between micro and macroeconomic reproduction is possible only with the market as a self-regulating system and with the regulatory investment activity of the state. The service sector is one of the most important structural elements of the modern economy. The development of this sector directly affects the level of economic growth and employment. Therefore, attracting investments to the service sector is one of the important strategic issues. However, various risks may arise in the process of attracting investments. This article analyzes the risks that arise when attracting investment in the service sector and foreign experience in managing them. Fundamentally improving the investment climate, reducing the state's participation in the economy, ensuring the inviolability of private property, and increasing its role and significance are important conditions for the sustainable development of the country's economy. In the current global economic climate, countries that have established

and implemented excellent investment policies are leading the world. For example, these countries include the G7 countries. The experience of Japan, the USA, Great Britain, Germany and France, in particular, is one of the most optimal solutions for investment activities. Their economic development strategies are countries whose economic development strategies can be the best experience for our country.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

A number of scientific research works have been conducted by foreign economists in this area. In particular, Y.S. Melkumov analyzed the effective use of financial, property and intellectual investments in financing investments in order to obtain profits in the development of production and entrepreneurship [1]. The author here studied investments as a source of income and indicated the types of investment activities. The controversial issue here is the types of investment objects. This has been discussed in our other scientific works.

S.V. Valdaytsev and P.P. Vorobyev analyzed the sources of financing for social investment. They concluded that the funds spent on social income generation processes are intended to generate higher income or social benefits in the future [2].

According to Prof. Y.M. Mirkin, a realistic, promising form of investment financing is to increase the placement of companies' savings from the secondary market into equity capital, but the level of this source of investment financing is very low [3].

The well-known economist W. Sharp also pays special attention to the mechanism of financing investment activities through the stock market. In his opinion, a rational investment strategy with a direct relationship between the profitability and riskiness of securities is the basis for financing investment activities. Financial intermediaries (commercial banks, savings and credit associations, credit unions, insurance companies, mutual funds, pension funds) indirectly provide corporations with the opportunity to attract additional funds from the stock market [4].

K.K. Khasanov has conducted a comparative analysis of the legal regimes, institutional norms and mechanisms of investment activity in developed foreign countries. Criteria for assessing investment activity and ways to increase the activity of regions in attracting foreign investment using the experience of foreign countries are proposed [5].

Associate Professor B.K. Tukhliyev's research considered a number of issues, including financing investment activities, the formation of their sources, the creation of a favorable investment environment, the study of factors affecting investment activities, and the improvement of the activities of enterprises with foreign investment. Conclusions and proposals were formulated on the composition, analysis, and improvement of investment activities and sources of financing them in the current conditions [6].

It should be noted that effective regulation of this sector is one of the most important ways to develop the country's economy. Therefore, it is important to conduct necessary research in this area and find ways to regulate investments and create mechanisms.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The article uses analytical and comparative methods. The experience of foreign countries in attracting investments in the service sector is studied, their risk management strategies are analyzed. Statistics from open sources, scientific articles, and reports of international organizations are also used.

Rating categories for each region of the country based on the ratio of total capacity and integral risk magnitudes

Group	Rating category
1A - group	High authority – minimal risk
1B - group	High-potential – moderate risk
1C - group	High authority – high risk
2A - group	Medium-strength – minimal risk
2B - group	Medium-capable – moderate risk
2C - group	Medium authority – high risk
3A1 - group	Has a low level of authority - has minimal risk
3A2 - group	Has insignificant authority - has minimal risk
3B1 - group	Low-level authority – moderate risk

3C1 - group	Low-level authority – high-level risk
3B2 - group	Has insignificant authority - has a moderate level of risk
3C2 - group	Has insignificant authority - has a high level of risk
3D - group	Low-level authority – extreme risk

During our research, we analyzed the processes of regulating investment activities in developed countries. According to our analysis, in the United States, investment processes are regulated by the state within certain limits. More than 22% of gross capital investments in the US economy are accounted for by states, of which 14% are allocated to investments from the federal budget. The state's influence on investment activities is carried out using such financial instruments as preferential income tax rates, accelerated depreciation policies, and incentives for selected categories of investments.

Due to the federal structure of the state, foreign investment in the United States is regulated in two ways: at the federal level and at the state level. At the federal level, general regulatory requirements are mainly established, and special regulatory requirements for the participation of foreign investors in projects in the territory of the respective states are established by local authorities. Each state operates in attracting foreign investment on the basis of local laws and long-term and short-term programs developed taking into account local characteristics and needs. Each state has its own programs for attracting domestic and foreign investment, since the federal government does not play an active role in determining the goals of economic development of a particular region of the country. Local authorities independently determine promising areas for the development of industrial sectors, both at the expense of state and borrowed funds.

The policy pursued in the United States, with some exceptions, is to ensure equal conditions for the management of foreign and domestic investors. For example, foreign investors can freely invest their funds in most sectors of the country's economy, as well as withdraw capital and profits.

In Europe, in particular in Germany and Sweden, investment projects are being implemented on the basis of social responsibility and corporate cooperation in order to minimize risk in the service sector. For example, companies make investments taking into account environmental and social accountability. This, in turn, reduces risk, as this model helps to maintain corporate reputation and develop strategies aimed at social progress.

Although there is no specific law regulating foreign investment in France, there is a system of "prior notification of the authorities of the intention to extend the approval period". This mainly applies to investors from non-EU countries engaged in the activities of a French company. In addition, French law clearly distinguishes between direct and other foreign investments, which is explained by the use of more favorable regulation in relation to the latter. This is because, despite the significant simplification of the procedure for regulating foreign investment, the majority of direct investment transactions in France still require prior notification of intention or prior authorization.

In Japan, intelligent platforms and "real-time" analysis have become popular in the service sector to minimize risk. With the help of such analytical tools, companies are able to identify development trends in advance and thus clearly see any risks. For example, many Japanese companies have implemented systems that allow them to quickly respond to changes in the market by installing real-time monitoring.

The main methods of regulating investment activities in the UK, France, Germany and Japan are as follows:

The main methods of regulating investment activities in the UK, France, Germany and Japan are as follows:

- regulation of the total volume of capital investments. This is the main method of managing the investment process, which is carried out through credit interest rate policy, monetary policy, tax and depreciation policy;
- selective promotion of investments in specific enterprises, sectors and areas of activity through credit and tax incentives, for example, investment loans;
- direct administrative intervention in the investment process in order to launch or withdraw certain production capacities by coordinating the plans of large corporations.

In France, relations between the state and the regions are built on a contractual basis within the framework of the national planning system. The state thus assists in the economic development of the regions. Each region concludes planned contracts with the state, which bind both parties to a specific investment program. Then they are included in the state's national plan as a priority task. At the same time, additional funds are being allocated to the most problematic regions. The implementation of such a policy is carried out in the form of restructuring the regional economy. For this purpose, investment grants are allocated to improve the infrastructure of the regions and create jobs in priority sectors of the economy.

To equalize the imbalance in the development of regions, the experience of state financing of France and Germany began to be actively used at the European Union level, for which a special Structural Fund of the

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. aprel. № 3. navbatdan tashqari son

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.

Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

El.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>